

Table 2. Correlation among root characters, root Fe content, and some biometric differentials with yield.

Root and biometric character	Yield			Root Fe content
	Grain	Straw	Total	
Shoot dry weight (PI-MT)	0.203	0.186	0.206	-
Root dry weight (PI-MT)	0.625**	0.631**	0.665**	-
Total dry weight (PI-MT)	0.422**	0.412	0.442**	-
Shoot dry weight (PI-MT)	0.609**	0.539**	0.610**	-
Root dry weight (FI-PI)	0.463**	0.494**	0.506**	-
Total dry weight (FI-PI)	0.629**	0.577**	0.640**	-
Root no. plant ⁻¹	0.748**	0.676**	0.757**	-0.607**
Av root length (cm)	0.402	0.358**	0.404**	-0.565**

PI = panicle initiation stage, MT = maximum tillering stage, FI = flowering stage. ** = significant at 0.01% level.

and the flowering and PI stages; shoot dry weight difference between the flowering and PI stages; total dry weight difference between the PI and MT stages; and average root length were also

highly correlated with grain yield, straw yield, and total biomass. The significant influence of average root length on yield demonstrated that average root length has a significant role in boosting yield.

A significant correlation observed between both root number and average root length and root iron content confirmed that Fe content and its deposition were the predisposing cause of low root development.

A correlation between biometric differentials and yield showed that root number plant⁻¹ at MT is the best index of future yield, which in turn suggests that inhibited root growth and/or decay is the best index of low yield of rice in lateritic soils.

Effects of temperature on fertility and seed set in intersubspecific hybrid rice

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Since intersubspecific hybrid rice showed strong heterosis in the past 12 years, many such hybrids were released for commercialization. However, some of them exhibited unstable seed set and limited grain yield under lower temperature. To use the strong heterosis in intersubspecific hybrids, it is necessary to study the reasons for their instability.

In this study, 11 intersubspecific hybrids, 1 indica hybrid, and 7 indica, japonica, or javanica inbred cultivars were used to investigate the effects of temperature on fertility and seed set, observe the variation in activity of male and female gametes, and look into suitable and safe temperatures (daily average) for the flowering stage.

All 11 intersubspecific hybrids, 2 indica cultivars, and 4 japonica or javanica cultivars showed a significant correlation between seed set and temperature. Results showed that the seed set of most rice hybrids and cultivars was sensitive to temperature, and that it was more sensitive in intersubspecific hybrids. When flowering within a temperature range of 13.7–29.3 °C (daily average), the seed set of intersubspecific hybrids would decrease by 6.74% ± 1.6% for each degree of temperature lower. This was significantly higher ($t = 3.14$, $n = 14$) than that of the four japonica or javanica cultivars (4.87% ± 2.7%).

Ten intersubspecific hybrids, two indica cultivars, and two japonica cultivars showed a significant correlation between pollen fertility and temperature. The pollen fertility of the 10 intersubspecific hybrids decreased by 3.42% ± 1.6% for each degree of temperature lower, was higher than that of the two japonica cultivars (1.40% ± 0.2%), and was close to that of the two indica cultivars (2.66% ± 2.9%).

The cross 3037/02428 (A172) exhibited a wide variation in spikelet fertility of 0–93% within a temperature range of 13.7–29.3 °C. The panicles, which flowered at 23.8 °C, showed a lower pollen fertility of 54.4% ± 14.9% for stained pollen grains; semifertile panicles were

produced with a seed set of 24.5% ± 3.6%. However, the male parent, 02428, which flowered at the same temperature, showed a stained pollen grain rate of 98.8% ± 3.5%. We pollinated the pollen of 02428 to the F₁ panicles of 3037/02428; the seed set of these F₁ panicles increased up to 81.2% ± 5.0%, while that of the self-pollinated panicles was lower at 24.5%. Female gametes appeared to still be functional for fertilization, whereas partial sterility of the pollen affected by the lower temperature led to a reduction in seed set. To stabilize seed set, it was important to increase the tolerance of male gametes for lower temperature.

The suitable and safe temperatures for flowering were calculated by a linear regression analysis between seed set and temperature, and by the assumed seed set at 85% and 70% for suitable and safe temperatures, respectively. The suitable and safe average daily temperatures of intersubspecific hybrids for flowering were 26.8 ± 1.9 and 24.6 ± 2.9 °C, respectively, which were significantly higher by 1.2 and 2.0 °C, respectively, than that of the six inbred cultivars (see table). Although most of the intersubspecific hybrids showed requirements for higher temperature for flowering and seed set, it was possible to obtain hybrids with wide climatic adaptability and high fertility stability through screening in intersubspecific hybrid rice breeding. Hybrid Liangyoupeijiu (65002), which showed high stability of seed set and is planted widely in southern China, had suitable and safe temperatures of 25.4 and 23 °C, respectively, close to the average of the six inbred cultivars.

Correlation analysis between seed set or pollen fertility and temperature, and suitable and safe average daily temperatures for flowering.

Rice type	Intersubspecific hybrid												Indica cultivar			Japonica cultivar			Javanica cultivar	
	Code	A2	A12	A23	A36	A114	A172	TA1	TA5	A910	A801	9311	IR36	S23	K58	G41	E32	W21		
Between seed set and temperature	r	0.864	0.899	0.731	0.875	0.791	0.855	0.789	0.902	0.869	0.904	0.882	0.474	0.540	0.774	0.824	0.710	0.703	0.802	0.714
	n	15	13	12	15	15	11	16	13	15	15	11	16	13	17	10	13	20	12	12
Between pollen fertility and temperature	r	0.514	-0.180	0.705	0.791	0.830	0.584	0.878	0.626	0.630	0.778	0.104	0.040	0.683	0.565	0.167	0.669	0.665	0.180	
	n	17	15	14	20	19	14	19	14	17	11	17	14	12	17	12	14	19	14	17
Suitable temperature (°C)		25.4	26.8	34.4	26.4	27.0	27.9	28.0	27.2	27.7	25.2	-	-	27.1	24.4	25.7	25.0	26.6	24.8	
Safe temperature (°C)		23.0	24.4	27.8	24.2	24.6	24.8	26.2	24.6	25.5	22.6	-	-	24.4	22.5	22.6	20.1	24.2	22.0	
Suitable temperature for 10 intersubspecific hybrids: 26.8 ± 1.9 °C*												Safe temperature for 10 intersubspecific hybrids: 24.6 ± 2.9 °C*								
Suitable temperature for 6 inbred cultivars: 25.6 ± 2.1 °C												Safe temperature for 6 inbred cultivars: 22.6 ± 3.1 °C								

Note: ns, * ** mean no significant difference and significant at the level of 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Code: 65002: Liangyoupeijiu (Peiai64S/9311); 65396: Peiai64S/E32; A2: IR36/Kanou 262; A12: Kasalath/Akikhikari; A23: Kanou 262/Kasalath; A36: Akamai 1/Kasalath; A114: Kasalath/Niken 1; A172: 3037/02428; TA1: Nanjing 11/02428; TA5: Nanjing 14/02428; S23: Kasalath; K58: Kanou 262; G41: Akamai 1; W21: Ketan Nangka; A910: Siyou422 (731A/Lunhui422); A801: Shanyou63 (Zhenshan97A/Ninghui63).